

Virtual assistants have more to offer than the average secretary or administrative assistant. When a new entrepreneur comes to the VA world they come with the skills they have garnered over several years or sometimes decades in their perspective specialty. This is from the kind of work they did prior to becoming a VA. You will find some VAs come to this industry with Associate Degrees, Bachelor Degrees, Master Degrees as well as PhD's.

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A VA specialty is; a VA who specializes in a particular field for a particular industry. The industry could be real estate brokers, real estate agents, writers, speakers, coaches, physicians, dentist, lawyers, professors, students, entrepreneurs, engineers, mortgage brokers and just about any field you can think of.

This is a small list of the different specialties that VAs have experience in;

Advertising

Accounting

Bookkeeper

Bankruptcy Petition Preparation

Customer Service

Digital Documentation

Event Coordinator

Ghost Writer

Graphic Designer

Logo Designer

Marketing

Paralegal

Program Coordinator

Project Manager

Real Estate

Sales

Social Media

Telemarketer

Transcriptionist

Travel Agent

Type Setter

Website Designer

When deciding on hiring a VA, check out their websites for their specific specialty.

Below are some words that can be used to find a VA that offers a specialty you may be looking for.

If you are an attorney you can use keywords such as Virtual Paralegal Assistant or Virtual Bankruptcy Assistant.

If you are a writer or you need copy for a blog or newsletter, you can use words such as Ghost Writer along with the common VA.

If you are a writer, you can use words such as Ghost Writer, Editor, or Proofreader with the common VA.

If you are a physician, you can use words such as Medical Transcription and Medical Billing along with the common VA.

If you are a CPA firm, you can use words such as Bookkeeper or Accountant along with the common VA.

Using these words to search for your specific specialty area along with the common "Virtual Assistant" will help you find the VA you need.

There are many more specialty VAs. It would take pages and pages to go through them all. This article is to give you an idea on what types of specialty VAs there are and the many years of experience they bring to your business.

With increasing opportunities on the internet, more and more people have full time jobs on the internet; there is nothing that cannot be done through internet. If you are tired of having unreliable secretaries or they simply can't do enough for you, you can simply hire a virtual office assistant on whom you will not spend a dime in the name of insurance and they will be able to do more than the live in secretary will ever do. An in-house secretary occupies a lot of space; something that lacks in small businesses or medium sized companies.

From a virtual office assistant you will be able to benefit from personalized services, without feeling that you are letting them know too much about you. Hiring a virtual office assistant is hiring a personal assistant who will not take bathroom or coffee break when you are not around to supervise them. He will be on call anytime to do whatever you require of him anytime. The virtual office assistant will remind you of the appointment you need to make with your dentist and maybe make a hotel reservation for your annual retreat.

He may even go to the extent of designing the new web page for your business website, something that you would have had to outsource if you had a live-in secretary. Whether your virtual secretary does some outsourcing for his services really isn't a bother to you.

If you have an in-house assistant, he/she may not have the skills or the experience needed by the firm from time to time. On top of that, you will have to make room for the person and the myriad of machinery that he/she will come with. A virtual office assistant works far from you. You will not be able to see eye to eye but they will always be at your beck and call.

The in-house assistant stays idle at some point in their working day, depending on the amount of work that is handled by the firm on a day to day basis. No matter how much time he/spends on the work that is assigned to him/her a live-in assistant will not do more than is required by the boss unless you plan to hike the pay. They may go on a go slow or decide to quit without a notifying you. A virtual office assistant on the other hand is only paid for the actual hours that he does the job and nothing extra. He will not become a headache since he has other clients whose needs he needs to cater for. All you do is give an assignment and a due date; and the work will be delivered. It is [virtual assistant services uk](#) cheaper to maintain a virtual office assistant since you will not have to pay some fees that come with having an in-house assistant.

A virtual office assistant is most of the time an assistant to many other people and since he/she has specialized on the work that he/she is doing, they are more likely to be more proficient and faster and have the latest tools to do their jobs. They have the latest software and they have a good support system. They pool their resources and help each other out when they are stuck.